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CHAIRE
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Sécurité des infrastructures critiques

Enhancing cybersecurity using Digital Twin and AI

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Hugo BOURREAU

Currently pursuing a co-supervised PhD between IMT Atlantique (France) and UQAC (Canada), I'm focusing on enhancing cybersecurity through Digital Twin and AI technologies.

My research aims to develop and highlight the potential of Digital Twin in a cyber context.

I'm currently working on a survey, gathering the state of the art of the domain.

PhD Supervisors:

- Fabien DAGNAT
- Marc-Oliver PAHL
- Fehmi JAAFAR

Context

Digital Twin for Cybersecurity:

- Representation of a reference system
- Dynamic and real-time
- Data exchange
- Processus of creation, maturity
- Implementation specific / Implementation dependent
- Monitor system's behavior
- Support decision-making

Hypothesis:

- Digital Twin in industrial context
- Improve system's security by detecting and preventing cyberattacks, even cascading ones

More information about my literature review here:
https://github.com/SkYiMITo/dt4sec_survey_slr

Fig 1: Topics of my survey

Fig 2: Feature selection of Digital Twin

Reproducibility of results

To ensure consistency and comparability, a common framework is essential:

- Use of standardized metrics to evaluate DT realism and performance
- Development of reusable components to simplify DT deployment
- Adoption of shared dataset and tools for reproducible experiments

Goals:

- Allow accelerated development of DT
- Enable collaboration around DT
- Be able to tell the concrete impact of DT over other tools

Attack detection and prediction

Anticipate and identify Cyber Threats:

- Detection of ongoing attacks (including side channels)
- Prediction of cascading effects in interconnected systems
- Analysis of system behavior before, during, and after intrusion

Methodology:

- Implement Secure Water Treatment (SWaT) System as a testbed
- Combine feature extraction, statistical methods and alert correlation to improve threat detection

Fig 3: Prediction methodologies

Fig 4: SWaT architecture

Future Work

Objectives:

- Model and simulate a Cyber-Physical System (CPS) using DT
- Create DT scenarios to test against a representative attack dataset

Approach:

- Integrate SWaT components (e.g., pump, controller)
- Simulate fixed dataset of real attacks (ransomware e.g. WannaCry, worm e.g. Stuxnet, ...)
- Evaluate DT performance in detecting and predicting sophisticated threats